

LESA: LLM-based Search Assistant for Comprehensive Information Retrieval

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Abstract

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) excels at providing accurate answers to user queries but remains limited in tasks that require comprehensive and structured lists of entities. We refer to this gap as Comprehensive Information Retrieval (CIR). CIR is challenging for standard RAG because it prioritizes high-precision retrieval and generates single-shot answers. This often leads to incomplete coverage when extensive lists of entities are required, particularly in domains such as healthcare, law, and academia, where information is distributed across multiple web pages. To address this limitation, we introduce LESA, an LLM-based search assistant that leverages a neural-symbolic query reformulation module with a RAG agent. LESA reformulates the search query into multiple sub-queries, executes multi-step retrieval, extracts a list of candidate entities, and synthesizes results into a structured search transcript. We evaluate LESA across three healthcare domains and compare it to strong LLM-augmented retrieval baselines. LESA achieves substantially higher coverage, improving recall by 58 percent compared to our strong baseline, NQR-RAG. Our findings demonstrate that an LLM-based search assistant, when combined with query reformulation and multi-step retrieval, can present a viable approach for CIR.

1 Introduction

Patients, caregivers, and health counsellors often need a comprehensive understanding of regional healthcare services, from hospital information to regional mental healthcare services, to make informed health decisions. However, this information is located across government portals, directories, and healthcare practitioners' websites, making it challenging for users to search and aggregate information from these web sources [1] [2]. In information retrieval (IR), this reflects an informational search intent [3], where the challenge is retrieving information across numerous web pages. This paper focuses on a specific aspect of this intent: the challenge of achieving comprehensive information coverage. We define this problem as CIR. Information retrieval systems retrieve a ranked list of web pages for well-defined queries. IR systems assume that a ranked list of web pages can satisfy users' information needs [4]. Consequently, most work in IR has focused on improving the retrieval of best-matched documents for a user query [5]. Question answering systems built on top of IR also rely on this assumption, returning the best match answer for users' questions. However, some users' queries are better answered with lists of entities rather than a single answer.

While list question answering provides concise answer sets, its output is often limited to capture the full set of entities required for CIR [6]. For instance, consider a search query that exemplifies a CIR task, where the goal is to find information about all mental health services in a specific region located across multiple web pages. While widely used information retrieval systems like Google and Bing are effective for navigational tasks, they often fall short for complex informational tasks.

Traditional IR systems primarily optimize for precision. High recall is also valued in some applications. However, these systems are not designed to achieve exhaustive coverage, which we refer to as comprehensiveness in this study. As a result, users spend considerable time and effort manually searching, extracting, and aggregating information from multiple web pages [7].

Recent advances in LLM-augmented retrieval have introduced new paradigms that can address these limitations, particularly through the synergy between LLMs and search engines [5] [8]. A prominent example is RAG [9] [10], which shifts the focus from retrieving relevant web pages to generating direct and contextually grounded answers. RAG has also been applied to other domains such as team formation [11], drug discovery [12], and tutoring [13]. These applications demonstrate RAG's ability to handle complex information needs, motivating us to explore its potential for our task, CIR.

While RAG is optimized to provide precise answers to a given query, it remains limited in addressing the challenge of CIR. This happens because existing RAG models miss query reformulations along the geographical and thematic dimensions and retrieve a limited number of web pages for each query, which is not enough when information is spread across various web sources, and lists of entities are needed from the web pages. This paper investigates how RAG can be extended to retrieve comprehensive information.

To address these limitations, we developed LESA, a novel LLM-based search assistant. LESA functions like a researcher, leveraging an LLM and a knowledge graph to reformulate search queries into multiple sub-queries. These sub-queries are then executed by a RAG model, which searches, reads, and extracts information from various web pages. By orchestrating this process throughout an entire

search session, LESA systematically constructs a structured and comprehensive overview of healthcare information, which it presents as a search transcript.

This study is guided by three primary research objectives that shape the investigation of LESA. First, we evaluate LESA’s ability to retrieve comprehensive information in the healthcare domain. Second, we investigate the impact of different query reformulation strategies on the performance of CIR. Finally, we assess the role of neural re-ranking in the overall effectiveness of LESA. Together, these objectives provide a structured framework for understanding and improving LESA’s capabilities for CIR.

This paper makes the following contributions. First, we identified the challenge of CIR in IR, then developed LESA, a novel framework for healthcare comprehensive information retrieval. Second, we collected and curated a new dataset for evaluation, as no publicly available dataset existed for this task. Third, we performed ablation studies to quantify the impact of query reformulation and neural re-ranking on LESA’s performance, providing key insights into the model’s behaviour.

2 Methodology

In this study, we consider the task of healthcare comprehensive information retrieval, where the objective is to retrieve a comprehensive list of healthcare information for a search query. Here, the term healthcare information refers to web-based textual data describing healthcare services, organizations, and related resources. Given a search query q_0 representing an information need, the task is to retrieve a list of healthcare information $S = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$ that collectively covers multiple facets of the search query. This ensures that all healthcare entities relevant to the search query q_0 are included in the search transcript S .

2.1 LLM-based Search Assistant

LESA addresses the healthcare CIR problem introduced in this study. LESA leverages a neural-symbolic query reformulation model and a RAG-based search agent to orchestrate a search session. A search session refers to the process

of issuing multiple reformulated queries for a given search query q_0 to the search agent.

As illustrated in **Figure 1**, LESA performs query reformulation using a knowledge graph and an LLM. This process generates a batch of semantically related reformulated queries, each capturing a different geographical aspect of the input search query. The reformulated queries are executed through a RAG-based search agent, which searches, reads, and extracts information from web pages to produce a search transcript.

The search transcript provides a structured and comprehensive list of healthcare information by consolidating information from multiple web pages into an organized list. During transcript synthesis, results retrieved from multiple subqueries were de-duplicated and merged using set operations. The set is a data structure that stores unique items only. While adding a service, if an identical service already existed in the set, it was not recorded in the transcript. This ensures each service appears only once in the final transcript. LESA is described in **Algorithm 1**, with **Figure 2** presenting an example of the workflow.

Algorithm 1: LLM-based Search Assistant

Input: query q_0

System Components: Retrieval R , LLM L , SPARQL endpoint K_{SPARQL} , Graph of triplets G

Output: Search Transcript S

1. Generate SPARQL:
 $q_{SPARQL} \leftarrow (q_0 \parallel SPARQL_{manual});$
 2. Execute SPARQL: $G \leftarrow K_{SPARQL}(q_{SPARQL});$
 3. Expanded regions: $E_R \leftarrow G;$
 4. Reformulate queries: $Q \leftarrow L(q_0, E_R);$
 5. Initialize transcript: $S \leftarrow \emptyset;$
 6. **foreach** $q_i \in Q$ **do**
 - a) Retrieve web pages: $W_i \leftarrow R(q_i);$
 - b) Extract entities and update search transcript:
 $S \leftarrow S \cup L(W_i \parallel <extract>);$
 7. Search transcript: $S \leftarrow L(S \parallel <Synthesize>);$
 8. **return** S
-

Figure 1 Architecture of LESA. The system has two modules: Query Reformulation and Search Agent. The query reformulation module converts the search query into multiple sub-queries. The number of sub-queries generated by the model is controlled by the parameter n , which manages the LLM-driven search session. The Search Agent retrieves, reads, and extracts information from web pages and records the results in a search transcript.

Figure 2 An illustrative example of the LESA’s Workflow. The input search query, “hospitals in Ontario”, aims to retrieve a comprehensive list of hospitals in the region. LESA reformulates the input query into n sub-region-specific queries, which are then used to search the top- k web pages. The LLM extracts hospital details from these pages and records them in a structured search transcript.

2.1.1 Neural-Symbolic query reformulation

Neural-Symbolic AI combines neural pattern recognition with symbolic reasoning. Recent work in this area includes advances using Hopfield neural networks with satisfiability logic rules [14] and logic mining [15]. A growing trend is the use of knowledge graphs as symbolic representations with neural models such as LLMs, enabling the strengths of both paradigms [16].

In this study, we propose a Neural-Symbolic (NeurSym) query reformulation model that combines the reasoning capabilities of a large language model (LLM) with symbolic knowledge from an RDF knowledge graph (DBpedia). Given an initial query q_0 , the module performs semantic expansion by identifying geographical aspects of the search query q_0 from DBpedia. Using SPARQL queries, DBpedia is queried to extract a graph of triplets (GOT), which is then fed into the LLM. **Figure 3** illustrates an example of a SPARQL query and the process by which DBpedia entities are extracted.

The LLM is then prompted using a combination of chain-of-thought and few-shot prompting with DBpedia entities. This process generates a batch of reformulated queries $Q = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n\}$ where each $q_i \in Q$ captures a distinct geographical dimension of the search query q_0 . The set Q is then passed to the search agent to retrieve healthcare information, enabling comprehensive coverage beyond single-answer retrieval.

Figure 3 Example SPARQL query illustrating how region-related entities are extracted from the DBpedia knowledge graph

2.1.2 Search agent

The search agent leverages RAG, which combines a retrieval model with the LLM. In the search agent architecture, the search engine serves as the retrieval model R that retrieves the top- k web pages for each reformulated query $q_i \in Q$. The LLM L then reads the text of the retrieved web pages and extracts healthcare information. LESA repeats this process for all queries $q_i \in Q$ generated by NeurSym and aggregates the resulting output in a text file defined as a search transcript S . The transcript provides structured and comprehensive healthcare information corresponding to the search query q_0 . The NeurSym model generates several reformulated queries determined by the parameter n , explained in **Section 3**. This parameter controls the LLM-driven session-level orchestration.

2.2 Baselines

To our best knowledge, there are no publicly available benchmarks and models that address the problem discussed in this study. For empirical evaluation, we developed multiple models and compared their performance against LESA, our proposed framework.

2.2.1 Retrieval-Augmented Generation

Recent studies have explored RAG architecture, in which a search engine serves as the retrieval model and the retrieved web pages are provided as contextual input to LLM for response generation [9] [10]. In our experiments, we modify the role of the LLM: instead of generating textual responses, the LLM is instructed to extract structured information from the retrieved web pages. This design choice is motivated by our observation that information extraction substantially reduces hallucination compared to response generation. Furthermore, we improved information extraction using Pydantic Base Model. When extracting struc-

tured information, such as fields, facts, or entities, from retrieved web pages, the use of Pydantic enforces data validation, type enforcement, and structured parsing, thereby improving the LLM’s precision in structured information extraction.

2.2.2 NQR-RAG

The Neural query reformulation (NQR) model employs an LLM that uses chain-of-thought prompting [17] and few-shot [18] learning for query reformulation. We observe that combining these two prompting strategies improves the model’s ability to reformulate search queries. The resulting batch of reformulated queries is then executed by the RAG, which retrieves the top-k web pages and extracts relevant information from them. The combination of NQR and RAG forms the NQR-RAG model.

2.2.3 Berry Picking Search Agent

The Berry-Picking Search Agent (BPSA) is inspired by Marcia Bates’ berry-picking model [4], which is designed to capture the iterative and evolving nature of information-seeking behaviour, where users continuously refine their queries and gather information in multiple stages. We operationalize this theoretical model using a large language model. The process begins with a query q_0 to the RAG, which retrieves the top-k web pages and extracts information from them. A set of three agents then analyses the retrieved information: one agent extracts thematic facets from the web pages, another performs keyword frequency analysis, and the third identifies relationships among the extracted keywords. The identified patterns and relations, along with the original query, are sent to the LLM for query reformulation. Then the reformulated query is passed to the RAG, and the process is repeated iteratively. The search process is repeated for a predefined number of iterations, denoted by the parameter n .

2.3 Evaluation metrics

To evaluate the performance of our models, we employ information retrieval metrics, Precision and Recall. The entities retrieved by the model are compared against those in the dataset. The exact match between the entities in the ground truth list and the model answers is considered a relevant entity. **Recall** measures all relevant entities retrieved by the model. A higher recall value indicates coverage of relevant entities relative to the testing dataset, reflecting the comprehensiveness.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Relevant entities retrieved by the model}}{\text{Total relevant entities present in dataset}}$$

Precision, on the other hand, quantifies the proportion of retrieved entities that are relevant. Higher precision values indicate that the model retrieves fewer irrelevant entities, reflecting its accuracy.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Relevant entities retrieved by the model}}{\text{Total entities retrieved by the model}}$$

During evaluation, we observe that the proposed model can retrieve entities that are not present in the dataset but are still relevant to the user query. Precision and recall do not account for such novel yet valid discoveries. To address

this limitation, we introduce an additional metric, **Discovery**, which captures these newly discovered relevant entities. We conduct a manual evaluation using Google Search to validate such results. For example, for the query *mental health services in a region Y*, if our model retrieves a mental health service in a region Y that is not present in the dataset, it is considered a valid discovery. **Usefulness** is defined as the ratio of all validated relevant entities (including both recalled and discovered ones) to the total number of entities retrieved by the model.

$$\text{Usefulness} = \frac{|\text{Recall} \cup \text{Discovery}|}{\text{Total entities retrieved by the model}}$$

3 Experiments

This study is situated within the context of the most populous province of Canada, Ontario. The area possesses a complex and varied information ecosystem, particularly in healthcare, offering a unique contrast, with more healthcare resources located in its southern region compared to the northern region. This dichotomy provides an ideal scenario to rigorously evaluate our models. Although our model was evaluated within the specific information ecosystem of Ontario, its architecture can be generalized to any region-specific and other health queries.

To evaluate the performance of LESA, we conducted a series of experiments comparing it against several models developed in this study. The details of these models are provided in **Section 2**. For all experiments, *GPT-4.1-2025-04-14* was employed for the query reformulation module, while *GPT-4.1-nano-2025-04-14* was adopted for information extraction. The temperature of the LLM was set to 0 to ensure reproducibility of the experiments. The LLM was accessed through the OpenAI API. Web pages retrieved through a programmable search engine accessed through the Google Search API, and the HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) content of web pages, were parsed using Beautiful Soup to extract textual data. To ensure a fair comparison, all models were evaluated under identical experimental conditions. Testing data used for evaluation is described in **Section 3.1**. Parameters for both the query reformulation and the search agent were kept consistent across models and detailed in **Section 3.2**. Evaluation metrics are detailed in **Section 2.3**.

3.1 Experimental data

To evaluate LESA in realistic healthcare scenarios, we constructed a dedicated testing dataset. Lists of healthcare entities across different healthcare domains, such as hospitals, addiction treatments, and mental health, were scraped from the Ontario 211 database [19], which maintains comprehensive inventories of social health, community, and government services in Ontario, and contains over 60,000 verified healthcare services listings. Several prior studies have also used Ontario 211 as an authoritative source for healthcare and community service information in Ontario, further supporting its suitability for research applications [20] [21].

We extracted the records relevant to healthcare data from the Ontario 211. For example, in the case of *addiction*

treatment centres located in Ontario, we extracted all services listed under the corresponding category. Each list in our dataset was then manually validated through a Google search. Service names that appeared ambiguous or duplicated were manually reviewed to determine the reason for their presence in the dataset. This verification was performed by examining additional metadata available in the 211 database, including service descriptions and geographic location. Only services whose metadata clearly aligned with the intended query were retained; ambiguous or non-corresponding services were excluded from the final dataset. Based on these validated lists, we formulate queries aligned with each healthcare domain (as shown in **Table 1**).

Table 1 Example of ground truth answer lists and corresponding queries in our dataset.

Query: List of hospitals in Ontario
Answers list:
[1] Sunny Brook Hospital
[2] Cambridge Memorial Hospital
[3] Guelph General Hospital
...
[152] Belleville General Hospital
Query: Addiction treatment centres located in Ontario
Answer list:
[1] Arrow Medicals
[2] Delta Health Clinics
...
[327] Goyeau Street Clinic
Query: Community mental health centres in Ontario
Answer list:
[1] Genesis Lodge
[2] CMHA – Thunder Bay
...
[327] Mental health connections

The final dataset comprises 1,341 healthcare entities, which serve as ground-truth relevance judgments for evaluating the retrieval performance of our models. The evaluation task was thus formulated, where search queries are used as input to the model, and the output is validated against the ground truth to calculate an exact match.

3.2 Model parameters

We introduced two controllable parameters, k and n , across all models discussed in this study. The parameter k was specific to the RAG and search agent and defined the number of web pages retrieved from the Web per query using the search engine. In our experiments, k was set to 10 for each reformulated query to manage the computational cost associated with processing textual information retrieved from web pages.

The second parameter n is applied to all models that incorporate a query reformulation module, except for the baseline RAG model. The parameter n determined the number of reformulated queries q_i that a model issued to complete a search session. In our experiments, n was set to 50 for all experiments. For example, for the query “mental health services in Ontario,” the model using query reformulation issued 50 reformulated queries, each query retrieving

$k = 10$ web pages. Using $n = 50$ gave us extensive insight into the model’s ability to perform a long search session.

4 Results and discussion

LESA was evaluated against NQR-RAG and BPSA across three healthcare domains: Hospitals, Mental Healthcare, and Addiction treatments. Each model was assessed using Recall, Precision, Discovery, and Usefulness, capturing coverage, relevance, novelty, and practical utility. We also conducted two ablation studies: LESA with or without query reformulation, and with or without neural re-ranking.

Table 2 Performance evaluation of the models

Models	Domains	Re-call	Preci-sion	Discov-ery	Useful-ness
LESA	Hospitals	0.61	0.30	0.17	0.47
	Mental Health	0.16	0.11	0.42	0.57
	Addiction	0.38	0.13	0.50	0.63
NQR-RAG	Hospitals	0.49	0.16	0.19	0.35
	Mental Health	0.07	0.04	0.37	0.43
	Addiction	0.18	0.05	0.48	0.61
BPSA	Hospitals	0.24	0.09	0.02	0.10
	Mental Health	0.09	0.07	0.28	0.21
	Addiction	0.06	0.03	0.38	0.42

As demonstrated in **Table 2**, LESA outperforms baselines across all healthcare domains. It achieved the highest recall and offered substantial gains over other models, with the largest relative improvements in the Mental Healthcare domain, and the largest absolute gains in Addiction support. Precision remained competitive, while Discovery and Usefulness were significantly higher than those of NQR-RAG and BPSA. These findings illustrate that LESA retrieved both common and long-tail services more effectively, providing a strong balance between coverage and relevance for the retrieval of comprehensive healthcare information.

Results in **Table 2** were obtained using $n = 50$, which provided sufficient iterations to evaluate each model’s ability to reformulate queries and sustain long search sessions. The results showed that **query reformulation played a major role** in model performance. BPSA relied on patterns and relations extracted by the LLM agents from the search iteration results, but this strategy produced reformulated queries that drifted from the original search topic, indicating that information from the previous search step alone was not a reliable approach for LLM-orchestrated search. NQR-RAG performed better because chain-of-thought and few-shot learning improved the model’s query reformulation ability. In contrast, **LESA** achieved the strongest performance by combining an LLM with a knowledge graph and by reformulating queries along the geographical dimension. These findings demonstrated that effective query reformulation was essential for LLM-driven search sessions. Results also showed that neural-symbolic integration, where the LLM provided contextual understanding

and the knowledge graph provided structured knowledge, significantly improved query reformulation, which is an architectural strength of LESA.

4.1 Ablation study

We conducted ablation studies to evaluate the impact of query reformulation and neural re-ranking on LESA’s performance. **Figure 4** shows the comparison of recall (coverage) for LESA with and without query reformulation across the healthcare domain. The results indicated that removing query reformulation significantly dropped recall across all healthcare domains. These findings highlight the role of query reformulation in enabling comprehensive information retrieval.

Figure 4 Ablation study results comparing the recall of LESA with and without query reformulation across multiple healthcare domains

We further examined the effect of neural re-ranking on LESA’s performance, as illustrated in **Figure 5**. After retrieving web pages for each reformulated query, we applied a cross-encoder [22] to re-rank twenty candidate web pages and selected the top ten from them. Neural re-ranking improved precision and usefulness by filtering noise and prioritizing relevant results. This showed that neural re-ranking was a critical component for making comprehensive information retrieval effective. We observed that retrieving web pages for neural re-ranking doubled the search API cost compared to retrieval without re-ranking. Given that the performance gains were relatively modest, neural re-ranking was less cost-effective for large-scale information retrieval systems.

Figure 5 Ablation study results illustrating the impact of neural re-ranking on the performance of LESA

4.2 Discussion

To better understand LESA’s performance, we conducted a detailed error analysis. In the hospital domain, LESA achieved the highest recall and precision. This performance was likely due to the relatively structured and centralized information in this domain, which resulted in fewer errors. In contrast, the performance of LESA substantially declined in the mental health domain. Mental health information encompasses a wide range of sub-services, such as counselling, depression support, psychotherapy, and other mental health resources.

LESA query reformulation strategy reformulated queries along geographical dimensions, which limited the coverage of information across those sub-categories. Expanding the query reformulating space to include both geographical and services subcategories would likely improve the performance of the model. However, this would also increase the computational cost of the model. The addiction treatment domain showed intermediate performance. These observations indicated that the degree of information fragmentation and domain heterogeneity were key factors that impacted the LESA’s performance.

5 Conclusion and future work

In this study, we propose an LLM-based search assistant that leverages query reformulation and RAG for comprehensive healthcare information retrieval. This study demonstrates the potential of LLM-driven session-level orchestration to provide structured and comprehensive healthcare information. Our experiments across various healthcare domains in Ontario indicate that LESA outperforms baseline models in recall, discovery, and usefulness, effectively retrieving both common and long-tail healthcare information.

Although our model is tested within the information ecosystem of Ontario, it is generalizable to any region. This is possible if the geographical information is present in the DBpedia Knowledge graph. For example, for a region-specific search query, such as addiction treatments in British Columbia (or any other region), LESA can incorporate the corresponding geographical context of the search query, provided that the region’s information is available in the DBpedia Knowledge graph.

Despite these strengths, LESA has several limitations. The performance of LESA can be influenced by search engine volatility. Moreover, the query reformulation module currently depends on manually curated SPARQL queries to retrieve information from an RDF knowledge graph. The model is also limited to reformulating search queries along geographical dimensions for which data exists in the DBpedia knowledge graph.

This study is an initial step toward search assistants for comprehensive healthcare information retrieval. Future work can explore automating SPARQL query generation, incorporating agentic retrieval strategies, and practical utility across other diverse healthcare domains.

6 References

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